

Coherent Beam-Beam Instability in Collisions with a Large Crossing Angle

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In recent years the “crab-waist collision” scheme [P. Raimondi, *Proceedings of 2nd SuperB Workshop, Frascati, 2006.*; M. Zobov *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **104**, 174801 (2010)] has become popular for circular e^+e^- colliders. The designs of several future colliders are based on this scheme. So far the beam-beam effects for collisions under a large crossing angle with or without crab waist were mostly studied using weak-strong simulations. We present here strong-strong simulations showing a novel strong coherent head-tail instability, which can limit the performance of proposed future colliders. We explain the underlying instability mechanism starting from the “cross-wake force” induced by the beam-beam interaction. Using this beam-beam wake, the beam-beam head tail modes are studied by an eigenmode analysis. The instability may affect all collider designs based on the crab-waist scheme. We suggest an experimental verification at SuperKEKB during its commissioning phase II.

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Recent and future e^+e^- colliders adopt a collision scheme with a large horizontal crossing (Piwinski) angle $\sigma_z\theta_c/\sigma_x \gg 1$ [1], where θ_c is the half crossing angle. The vertical beta function is squeezed below the value of the rms bunch length, $\beta_y^* < \sigma_z$, while the crossing angle is chosen as $\sigma_x/\theta_c \leq \beta_y$ to avoid the hourglass effect [2–4]. Crab-waist collision [4,5] achieves a nearly perfect suppression of the hourglass effect for particles with a large horizontal amplitude.

Beam-beam effects for a large-crossing-angle-crab-waist collision were extensively studied using weak-strong simulations. In these simulations a very high beam-beam parameter ($\xi_y > 0.1$) was achieved for the designs of Super B factories [6] and of the e^+e^- Future Circular Collider (FCC-ee) [7,8]. In a weak-strong simulation one (strong) beam has a fixed charge distribution, so that the incoherent emittance growth of the other (weak) beam can be analyzed. On the other hand, in early 2016 strong-strong simulations revealed a novel coherent beam-beam instability of the head-tail type [9,10]. This instability was observed only when using the strong-strong simulation code “BBSS” [11]. Since the second half of 2016 there has been progress on three fronts: First, another BBSS simulation suggested that this new instability can be experimentally studied at SuperKEKB, during its upcoming phase II of commissioning. Second, it was demonstrated analytically that the cross-wake force induced by beam-beam collisions under a large crossing angle can cause a strong head-tail instability. These

two subjects are discussed in the present Letter. Third, D. Shatilov observed the same instability using the code “Lifetrack,” based on a quasi-strong-strong model [12,13]. In view of all these findings the instability phenomenon appears to be real. The novel instability may have a strong impact on the design of all future colliders based on large-crossing-angle-crab-waist collision.

The coherent head-tail mode induced by beam-beam interaction without crossing angle has been discussed in Ref. [14]. The head-tail motion was induced by a correlation between the head and tail of a bunch due to a large vertical disruption parameter, $D_y = 2\pi\xi_y\sigma_z/\beta_y$. By contrast, in a collision with a large Piwinski angle, the coherent instability is induced in the horizontal plane, and a strong-strong beam-beam simulation is necessary to study this coherent beam-beam effect. We use the code BBSS, where two colliding bunches are represented by many macroparticles ($\sim 1M$) and the collision is modeled via the interactions between the particle distributions. Each bunch is divided into many slices along the longitudinal direction to simulate the collision with a large crossing angle and any resulting head-tail motion. The extension to 3D of the slice-by-slice bunch collision is described in Ref. [15]. Typically the number of slices is chosen as $n_{sl} \approx 10\sigma_z\theta_c/\sigma_x$.

We study the coherent beam-beam instability for SuperKEKB and FCC-ee, considering the parameters of Table I [16]. We first report the instability seen in the simulation, and then present a theoretical explanation based on the beam-beam induced cross-wake force.

Phase I commissioning of SuperKEKB started in February, 2016 without the interaction region (IR) [17]. Beam-beam collision schemes with large crossing angles will be examined in the phase II commissioning that begins in 2018 after installation of the IR. The beta

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TABLE I. Parameters for SuperKEKB and FCC-ee.

Parameter		SuperKEKB		FCC-ee-Z		<i>H</i>
		Design	Commissioning	HiLum	Base	
Energy	$E_{+/-}$ (GeV)		4/7	45.5	45.5	120
Bunch population	$N_{+/-}$ (10^{10})	9/6.5	6.3/5	10	3.3	8
Emittance	$\varepsilon_{x/y}$ (nm/pm)	3.2/8.64	3.2/44	0.2/1	0.09/1	0.61/1.2
Beta at IP	$\beta_{x/y}^*$ (m/mm)	0.03/0.3	0.25/2.2	0.5/1	1/2	1/2
rms bunch length	σ_z (mm)		6	6.7	3.8	2.4
Energy spread	σ_δ (%)		0.08	0.22	0.09	0.12
Damping time	τ_x/T_0		4000		3000	150
Synchrotron tune	ν_z		0.025	0.036	0.025	0.056
Luminosity per IP	L (10^{34} cm^{-2} s^{-1})	80	...	207	90	5.1
Beam-beam parameter	$\xi_{x/y}$	0.0028/0.088	...	0.025/0.16	0.05/0.13	0.08/0.14
Piwinski angle	$\sigma_z\theta_c/\sigma_x$	20	8.7	10	6	1.5

functions at the interaction point (IP) will be squeezed sequentially in several steps [18]. The design values are extremely small, $(\beta_x^*, \beta_y^*) = (30, 0.3)$ mm. The phase II target is approximately $(\beta_x^*, \beta_y^*) = (240, 2.4)$ or $(120, 2.4)$ mm, that is, they are $(8\times, 8\times)$ and $(4\times, 8\times)$ of the design, respectively.

A strong-strong simulation was performed using these β^* values. The beam-beam parameter, calculated as normalized luminosity, i.e., $\xi_L = 2r_e\beta_y L / (N_e\gamma f_{\text{rep}})$, is used as an indicator of the beam-beam limit.

No unstable behavior was seen for the SuperKEKB design parameters with very small β_{xy}^* [19]. We, therefore, focus on the commissioning stage. Figures 1(a) and 1(b) show the beam-beam parameter and head-tail motion $\langle xz \rangle$, respectively, for β^* enhanced $(8\times, 8\times)$ and $(4\times, 8\times)$. Simulations were performed with and without the crab waist [CW (NoCW)]. A strong coherent beam-beam instability is seen with $(8\times, 8\times)$, but not with $(4\times, 8\times)$. This difference of $(8\times, 8\times)$ and $(4\times, 8\times)$ can be observed in the SuperKEKB commissioning. The crab waist is not a primary reason for the instability, but it has an effect on the luminosity.

The design of the FCC-ee-*H* aims for a beam-beam parameter of $\xi_y \sim \xi_L = 0.14/\text{IP}$. Because the FCC-ee has two IPs, we used a half ring model with 50 km circumference and doubled the dimensionless damping time in

FIG. 1. Strong-strong simulation results for SuperKEKB. (a) and (b) show the beam-beam parameter and head-tail motion $\langle xz \rangle$, respectively, at the commissioning stage with IP beta, $(8\times, 8\times)$, and $(4\times, 8\times)$.

the simulation. The Piwinski angle (PA) is $\sigma_z\theta_c/\sigma_x = 1.5$ in the design. The simulation is performed for the half crossing angles $\theta_c = 0.015$ and 0.02 rad (PA = $\sigma_z\theta_c/\sigma_x = 1.5$ and 2) to investigate the effects of the Piwinski angle. The tune operating point for the half ring is $(\nu_x, \nu_y) = (0.54, 0.61)$, which has been optimized by weak-strong simulations [20,21].

Figure 2 presents the simulation results for the FCC-ee-*H*. Figures 2(a) and 2(b) show the evolution of the beam-beam parameter for $\sigma_z\theta_c/\sigma_x = 1.5$ and 2, respectively. Bunch populations of 4 – 16×10^{10} are examined, while the design value is 8×10^{10} . The coherent motion of $\langle xz \rangle$ is not seen for PA = 1.5, but it is observed for PA = 2. Figure 2(c) shows a summary of the equilibrium beam-beam parameters. The error bars depict the fluctuations due to coherent motion. The beam-beam parameter is saturated at approximately

FIG. 2. Beam-beam simulation results for FCC-ee-*H* obtained by the full PIC strong-strong method. The evolutions of the beam-beam parameter for PA = 1.5 and 2 are shown in (a) and (b), respectively. The final beam-beam parameters as a function of bunch population (N_e) and the stationary horizontal beam size as functions of N_e and β_x^* are summarized in (c) and (d), respectively.

0.12 in both PA = 1.5 and 2, independently of the occurrence of coherent instability. The value of β_x^* is the key parameter for the coherent instability in SuperKEKB. Simulations for various values of β_x^* were performed, while keeping the horizontal beam size at the IP constant (by adjusting the horizontal emittance). Figure 2(d) shows the stationary horizontal beam size for various values of N_{\pm} and β_x^* . The stationary beam size depends on the product $N_{\pm}\beta_x^*$. At the design β_x^* , the beam size increases for $N_{\pm} \geq 2-3 \times 10^{10}$ [$N/N_{\text{design}} \geq 0.25$ in Fig. 2(d)], which is taken to be the threshold of an instability. Indeed, a coherent excitation of the second moment $\langle xz \rangle$ in the early stage of the simulation seems to be the cause of this beam size increase. Following the beam size increase the coherent motion disappears for PA = 1.5, and also for PA = 2, up to a second threshold. For PA = 2, at higher bunch intensities of $N_{\pm} \geq 6 \times 10^{10}$, the coherent motion persists even after, or with, the beam size increase.

The FCC-ee Z factory is designed with a larger Piwinski angle of PA = 6 or 10. The target beam-beam parameter is 0.13 or 0.16, for PA = 6 or 10, respectively. The tune operating point for the half ring is $(\nu_x, \nu_y) = (0.54, 0.61)$.

The coherent motion in $\langle xz \rangle$ is seen even at low current, where the thresholds are $N_{\pm} = 1.3 \times 10^{10}$ (40% of the design) and 3×10^{10} (30% of the design) for PA = 6 and 10, respectively. Figure 3 presents the simulation results for FCC-ee-Z. Figure 3(a) displays the beam-beam parameter as a function of the bunch population. The error bars depict the fluctuation in luminosity. The beam-beam parameter saturates at 0.1 and 0.04 at PA = 6 and 10, respectively. The limit value $\xi_L = 0.04$ at PA = 10 is very low. The coherent instability is more serious for larger Piwinski angles.

Figure 3(b) shows the beam-beam parameter as a function of β_x^* . We hold the horizontal IP beam size constant, and consider the design bunch population. The coherent instability and luminosity fluctuation disappear at $\beta_x^* \leq 0.08$ m for both PA = 6 and 10. The luminosity or beam-beam parameters recover their design values of 0.12 and 0.15 for PA = 6 and 10, respectively, at $\beta_x^* \leq 0.08$ m.

The two bunch tilts $\langle xz \rangle$ of the unstable e^+ and e^- beams always oscillate in phase, for SuperKEKB, FCCee-H, and Z; i.e., in all cases coherent beam-beam instability occurs for the head-tail “ σ ” mode.

FIG. 3. Simulation results for FCC-ee-Z. (a) the beam-beam parameter as a function of the bunch population, (b) the beam-beam parameter as a function of β_x^* .

For an understanding of the coherent instability, we introduce a cross-wake force caused by the beam-beam interaction. The cross-wake force mediates the correlation between two colliding bunches. Figure 4(a) illustrates how we evaluate the wake force. Namely, we consider two bunches tilted by half crossing angle in the x - s plane which collide with each other by moving in the opposite s direction. Without any translational motion in the x direction, for longitudinal position z_{\pm} the horizontal position of the bunch center is $x_{\pm} = \theta_c z_{\pm}$. We assume a deviation of Δx_- in part of the e^- bunch. A part of the e^+ bunch with z_+ interacts with the part of the e^- bunch with equal s , $s = (z_+ - z_-)/2$. The perturbed momentum kick of that part of the e^+ bunch is expressed by

$$\Delta p_x^{(+)} = -\frac{n_- r_e}{\gamma_+} [F_x(x_+ - x_- - \Delta x_-) - F_x(x_+ - x_-)], \quad (1)$$

where F_x is given by the Bassetti-Erskine formula [22] with asymptotic form $F_x \rightarrow 2/x$ for large x . n_- is the number of electrons contained in the associated part of the e^- bunch. The momentum kick for the static case, i.e., without any deviation of the e^- bunch, is subtracted. For a flat beam, F_x only weakly depends on $y \approx O(\sigma_y)$. The momentum kick $\Delta p_x^{(+)} = -W_x^{(+)}(z_+ - z_-)\rho_x^{(-)} \Delta z_-$ is represented through a “cross-wake” force $W^{(+)}$ as

$$W_x^{(+)}(z_+ - z_-) = -\frac{N_- r_e}{\gamma_+} \left. \frac{\partial F_x}{\partial x} \right|_{x=(z_+ - z_-)\theta_c}. \quad (2)$$

The wake force W_x is shown in Fig. 4(b). Above, $\rho_x^{(-)}(z)$ is the longitudinal density distribution of the horizontal dipole moment. An important relation links horizontal and longitudinal displacements: $n_- \Delta x_- = N_- \rho_x^{(-)} \Delta z_-$. The momentum kick is obtained by integrating over the dipole moment density of the opposite bunch:

$$\Delta p_{x,\pm}(z_{\pm}) = -\int_{-l}^l W_x^{(\pm)}(z_{\pm} - z'_{\mp}) \rho_x^{(\mp)}(z'_{\mp}) dz'_{\mp}. \quad (3)$$

The minimum cross wake is $W_x^{(\pm)}(0) \approx -N_{\mp} r_e / (\gamma_{\pm} \sigma_x^2)$ at $z = 0$, where $\sigma_x^2 = (\sigma_{x+}^2 + \sigma_{x-}^2)/2$.

FIG. 4. (a) Illustration of the evaluation of the wake force induced by the beam-beam interaction, and (b) obtained wake force for FCC-ee-Z (PA = 10).

FIG. 5. Growth rate for each eigenmode [FCC-ee-Z (PA = 10)] as a function of the eigenmode tune, for a bare tune $\nu_x = 0.54$.

We consider the σ mode, in which dipole moments are equal, $\rho_x^{(+)}(z) = \rho_x^{(-)}(z)$, and the π mode, in which they are opposite [$\rho_x^{(+)}(z) = -\rho_x^{(-)}(z)$], where the transparency conditions $N_+\gamma_+ = N_-\gamma_-$, $\sigma_{+,xyz} = \sigma_{-,xyz}$, $\nu_{+,xyz} = \nu_{-,xyz}$ are assumed. Equation (3) then reduces to the usual formula for the wake force of a single bunch,

$$\Delta p_x(z) = \mp \int_{-l}^l W_x(z-z')\rho_x(z')dz, \quad (4)$$

where the $-(+)$ sign is chosen for $\sigma(\pi)$ modes, respectively.

A mode analysis for the horizontal dipole moment can now be carried out in longitudinal phase, using

$$x_{ij} = x(J_i, \phi_j), \quad p_{ij} = p_x(J_i, \phi_j), \quad \psi_i = \psi(J_i), \quad (5)$$

where ψ is the density distribution in longitudinal phase space, $\psi = \exp(-J/\varepsilon_z)/(2\pi\varepsilon_z)$. The longitudinal phase space is discretized as [23]

$$J_i^{1/2} = i\Delta J^{1/2}, \quad \phi_j = 2\pi\nu_s j, \quad z_{ij} = \sqrt{2\beta_z J_i} \cos \phi_j, \quad (6)$$

where $i = 1, n_J$, $j = 1, 1/\nu_s$. For simplicity $1/\nu_s$ is assumed to be an integer. Effects of synchro-betatron resonances are determined by the relation between synchrotron and betatron tunes, and our assumption for $1/\nu_s$ does not constrain this relation. For one arc revolution, the transverse betatron oscillation is modeled by a matrix transformation for (x_{ij}, p_{ij}) , as

$$M_0 = \delta_{i,i'}\delta_{j-1,j'} \begin{pmatrix} \cos 2\pi\nu_x & \sin 2\pi\nu_x \\ -\sin 2\pi\nu_x & \cos 2\pi\nu_x \end{pmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

where $\nu_x = 0.54$. The synchrotron motion is represented by transforming with the Kronecker delta, $\delta_{j-1,j'}$. The transformation for the momentum kick due to the wake force is expressed by

$$M_W = \begin{pmatrix} \delta_{i,i'}\delta_{j,j'} & 0 \\ -\beta_x W(z_{i,j} - z_{i',j'})\psi_{i'}\Delta J\Delta\phi & \delta_{i,i'}\delta_{j,j'} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

Stability of the colliding bunches is discussed by eigenvalues/vectors of the matrix product $M_W M_0$, where the size of matrices is $(2 \times n_J \times 1/\nu_s)^2$. $n_J = 40$, $\Delta J^{1/2} = 0.05\varepsilon_z^{1/2}$,

TABLE II. Threshold bunch intensities in units of 10^{10} obtained using three different approaches.

Collider	BBSS	Mode analysis	Tracking
FCC-ee-Z HiLum	2–3	1.2	1.2
FCC-ee-H	2–3	2.3	2.1

$1/\nu_s = 56$ are chosen for FCCee-Z (PA = 10). The size of matrices is 4480^2 . Eigenvalues (λ 's) are plotted in Fig. 5, where the growth rate per revolution and tune are given by $\log|\lambda|$ and $\tan^{-1}(\text{Im}\lambda/\text{Re}\lambda)/(2\pi)$, respectively. Figure 5(a) shows the growth rate for σ/π modes. All of the π modes are stable. Pairs of growth and damping modes are seen in the σ modes. The unstable tunes are $0.5 + m\nu_s$, $m \leq 14$. The most unstable mode is at $\nu = 0.5$. Figure 5(b) shows the growth rate for changing strengths of the wake force: $1/2$, $1/5$, and $1/10$ of the nominal. The unstable modes disappear at $1/10$. This instability is a phenomenon with a threshold.

We also performed particle tracking simulations of two bunches or a single bunch modeling the collision with the cross-wakes of Eqs. (3) and (4), respectively, and the rest of the ring by a simple revolution matrix, using self-developed programs in FORTRAN or C++, and considering 10 000 macroparticles per bunch. A numerical comparison of instability thresholds obtained by the three different methods is presented in Table II.

In conclusion, we studied coherent beam-beam effects with a large Piwinski angle and crab-waist collision using a strong-strong simulation code, BBSS. Simulations for SuperKEKB, FCC-ee-H, and FCC-ee-Z show a strong coherent beam-beam instability in the head-tail σ mode. The coherent instability is of an acceptable magnitude for the SuperKEKB design parameters and for FCC-ee-H, but it is serious for FCC-ee-Z. The existence and threshold of this instability can be experimentally verified during the SuperKEKB commissioning with a relaxed β_x^* (which is presently scheduled for the spring of 2018). Squeezing β_x^* helps mitigate the instability. As a result of our study, the base line parameters of the FCC-ee-Z have been changed to $\beta_x^* = 0.15\text{--}0.2$ m and $\varepsilon_x = 260$ pm [13]. A theoretical model based on the beam-beam wake force can explain this instability. The associated mode-coupling analysis reveals unstable head-tail σ modes. Controlling this instability is essential for the design of future lepton colliders, such as FCC [24], CEPC [25], BINP charm-tau [26], SuperKEKB [17], etc.

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